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THE LEVEL OF MATHEMATICS ANXIETY OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS IN CARLOS L. ALBERT HIGH SCHOOL: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

One of the duties of educators is to identify where the students are having difficulty with the lesson and find ways to help them easily cope with it. One of the common students' problems is their low performance in mathematics. Several issues are anchored to this, and the researcher decided to focus on mathematics anxiety. To address this issue, the researcher sought the help of experts like psychologists, guidance counselors, homeroom advisers, and parents through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, which were conducted regularly.

Mathematics anxiety pertains to students' feelings of tenseness or nervousness while working on numbers or problem solving in mathematics. Students who suffer from mathematics anxiety do not necessarily experience anxiety in other subjects. It is affirmed that achievement in mathematics is conversely proportional to their anxiety. The result of the study bears a resemblance to a study cited by **Banguis and Abao (2018)**, which found that another factor that might hinder students from learning mathematics is their anxiety about the subject. Hence, the researcher aimed to use macro-lessons, interactive games, and innovative instructional material to present a variety of strategies for the students to enjoy while learning and improve their achievement.

The subject of the study was limited to the 25 students who were identified with mathematics anxiety out of the 150 students who took the Self-Test Anxiety in Mathematics questionnaire. The students took the pre-test covering the lessons in the 3rd quarter before the utilization of the instructional material. A post-test and self-test anxiety in mathematics questionnaire were also given after the lessons. The results showed that there are 12 students with severe anxiety and 13 with moderately severe anxiety. Thus, the utilization of Instructional Material 12 resulted in two students with severe anxiety. Meanwhile, 8 with severe anxiety became moderately severe anxiety. Hence, there are now 21 cases of moderate to severe anxiety.

The number of students with severe anxiety levels decreased, which in turn became moderate to severe anxiety after the utilization of the instructional material. There are three features of innovative instructional material. There is a significant difference in the level of anxiety before and after the utilization of the instructional material. Findings also show that innovative instructional material was assessed as strongly agreed upon by the math teachers

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and guidance counselors. Significant features of innovative instructional material may be considered in the development of instructional materials, and these may also help the students understand the lesson with ease.

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